

Fatigue Behaviour of Pressurized Filament Wound Fibreglass/Epoxy Tubes

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the experimental results on fatigue behaviour of filament wound fibreglass/epoxy tubular specimens. The tests were conducted at room temperature through application of cyclic internal pressure at a frequency of 0.417 Hz (or 25 cpm). Two pressure ratios (p_{min}/p_{max}) of 0.05 and 0.3 were used. The hysteresis loops and fatigue lives in terms of cycles to failure were recorded and analyzed. The results are discussed with respect to changes in the slope of hysteresis loops, cyclic ratcheting and the observed micro-damage.

INTRODUCTION

Composite tubulars relative to conventional carbon steel products offer a life cost savings due to their superior corrosion and fatigue resistance, ease of fabrication and installation. However, no proven method exists for determining their long-term fatigue strength characteristics under varied loading conditions [1]. Most studies are directed towards an experimental determination of monotonic failure envelopes for thin walled cylinders with only a few wound layers [2-8].

For pressurized components "leakage before fracture", is usually adopted as an operational definition of failure. This type of failure is associated with the matrix cracking and delamination, i.e. the failure mode is matrix dominated.

Most engineering tubing installations are subjected to both alternating pressure (or pressure range) and mean pressure during their service life. In general, an increase in the mean pressure (or pressure ratio $R = \text{min. pressure}/\text{max. pressure}$) is detrimental.

The objective of this study is to investigate experimentally the deformation behaviour and effect of mean pressure on fatigue life of composite tubes. The tests were conducted at room temperature with two pressure ratios $R = 0.05$ and 0.3 . The cyclic pressure-strain hysteresis loops and fatigue lives in terms of cycles to failure were recorded and analyzed. Cyclic creep (ratcheting) and changes in the slope of hysteresis loops in both transverse and axial directions due to the accumulation of fatigue damage, are investigated.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMENS

Filament wound tubes manufactured by commercial firms were used in this study. These tubes had a complex winding pattern as illustrated in Fig. 1. The actual lay-up of these tubes was $[\pm 70, \pm 45_2, -70, 0, +45, \pm 45_4]$ (seventeen layers). The off axis orientations were filament wound producing helices at the desired angle θ to the tube axis. The 0° layer was produced by placing 102 mm (4 inch) strips on the tubes in a spiral pattern which overlapped the strip. The reinforcement used was a filament of "E" type glass within an epoxy resin. The volume fraction of fibres was determined to be $\sim 58\%$. A micrograph of a cross-section of the tube wall is shown in Fig. 2. It can be observed that there are certain amount of voids and some resin rich areas around the 0° layer. Also, a thin protective resin coating is present on the outside surface of the tube. The tubes have an inside radius, $r_i = 24.65$ mm a wall thickness, $t = 5.8$ mm. A 305 mm (12 inch) test section was cut from a long section of tube.

Figure 1 Multidirectional Tubular Specimen Lay-Up & Geometry

A biaxial testing apparatus, described in detail in Ref. 9 was developed to test the fibreglass/epoxy tubular specimens under various loading conditions. This testing facility is capable of applying up to 375 kN axial load in tension or compression, and 83 MPa internal pressure. Since the test tubes have no built up ends, a specially designed gripping system shown in Fig. 3, was designed [9].

Figure 2 Micrograph of undamaged specimen

Figure 3 Schematic of Grip Assembly

development will be the subject of a future paper.

TEST PROCEDURE

The fatigue test were conducted at room temperature with a constant frequency of 0.417 Hz (or 25 cpm) by initially applying a mean pressure to the specimen and then superimposing an alternating pressure. Two pressure ratios were used: R = 0.05 and 0.3. For the first series of tests, with R = 0.05, the maximum operating pressure was ranged from: 55.2, 48.3, 27.6 and 20.7 MPa (or 8000, 7000, 4000 and 3000 psi) for each tube tested. An R ratio of 0.3 was chosen for the second series of tests so as to investigate the effect of higher R ratio (or mean stress) on the fatigue behaviour. The maximum operating pressure was kept similar to the first series of tests. As the tube's ends are capped, the internal pressure, p, induces a hoop stress, σ_H , an axial stress, σ_A , and a radial stress, σ_R . The radial stress $\sigma_R = -p$ at the inside radius (r_i), and $\sigma_R = 0$ at the outside radius (r_o) of the tube, and it is much smaller than σ_H (or σ_A). The hoop and axial stresses, induced by the applied pressure can be calculated adopting thin walled cylinder theory:

$$\sigma_H = p \frac{(2r_o - t)}{2t}, \tag{1}$$

and

$$\sigma_A = p \frac{r_i^2}{(r_o^2 - r_i^2)} \tag{2}$$

In the tests conducted, the ratio of hoop to axial stress, $\sigma_H:\sigma_A$, was kept constant and equal to ~2.5:1.

An IBM-PC computer was used to provide a sinusoidal load signal and to monitor and record test variables such as transverse and axial strains, pressure and oil volume. The change in oil volume was used to help detect when leakage initiates in the tubular specimens.

TEST RESULTS

The fatigue tests results are summarized in Table 1

TABLE 1. Summary of Fatigue Tests

Test	R Ratio	Maximum Pressure (MPa)	Cyclic Frequency Hz	Failure (Weepage) Cycle	Last Recorded Cycle
1	0.05	55.2	0.417	43	115
2	0.05	48.3	0.417	87	290
3	0.05	27.6	0.417	2,500	5,086
4	0.05	20.7	0.417	30,000	47,863
5	0.3	55.2	0.417	70	116
6	0.3	48.3	0.417	250	368
7	0.3	27.6	0.417	5,800	13,947

OIL VOLUME CHANGES

The oil volume change versus number of cycles is depicted in Fig. 4 for the first series of tests with $R = 0.05$. The tests with higher maximum pressure indicate that the slope of these curves changes gradually while the tests with lower pressure demonstrate a sharp "knee" transition in the slope change. A similar trend is observed for the second series of tests with higher pressure ratio, $R = 0.03$. The change in the slopes corresponds to the weepage of oil through the tube wall which was observed visually during the tests.

Figure 4 Oil volume changes for tubes tested at $R = 0.05$

HYSTERESIS LOOPS

Figures 5 through 7 show typical hysteresis loops obtained for the two sets of tests, with $R = 0.05$ and 0.3 .

Figure 5a shows the loops for the maximum pressure of 52.2 MPa (or 8000 psi) and an R ratio of 0.05. Although data were recorded until loop 100, the failure cycle was determined to be cycle 43. This was due to oil weepage through the wall of the pipe. For the same tests, loops for the axial strain vs. pressure are shown in Fig. 5b. These two figures show significant cyclic ratcheting in the transverse direction and stiffness changes, ie. "softening", in the transverse as well as axial directions.

Figure 5 Hysteresis loops for $R = 0.05$ and $p_{max} = 55.2$ MPa
 (a) axial strain vs pressure, (b) transverse strain vs pressure

For tests with the lower pressure, the change in the tube's stiffness was negligible. Therefore, only one graph of pressure vs. transverse strain is presented. The next two plots, (Figs. 6 and 7) display the loops obtained for the maximum operating pressure of 27.6 MPa (or 4000 psi) for R ratios of 0.05 and 0.3, respectively. These two figures again show a significant cyclic

Figure 6 Hysteresis Loops for $R = 0.05$ and $p_{max} = 27.6$ MPa

Figure 7 Hysteresis Loops for $R = 0.3$ and $p_{max} = 27.6$ MPa

ratcheting in the transverse direction. The failure cycle, due to weepage, was determined to be 2,500 for $R = 0.05$ and 5,800 for $R = 0.3$.

Although the life of the tested tubes ranged from 43 to 5,800 cycles, Figs. 5a, 6 and 7 show that ratcheting strain in the transverse direction was of the same magnitude. This indicates the significance of monitoring the strain and its importance in the development of failure criteria for composite tubes.

MICROSCOPIC OBSERVATIONS

Discussion regarding microscopic observations will be confined to tests performed at the lower pressure ratio, $R = 0.05$. Similar damage patterns were observed for the tests at higher R ratio. Small samples were extracted from the weepage area in order to examine the damaged material. Micrographs shown in Figs. 8a and b compare the 55.2 MPa and 27.6 MPa maximum pressure tests, respectively. In both cases extensive delamination through the 0° layer is seen. Delamination was also apparent between the inner $\pm 45^\circ$ layers (see Fig. 1) for the highest pressure test (55.2 MPa). In this region more extensive transverse matrix cracking is present in comparison to $\pm 45^\circ$ layers which are located between the 0° layer and $\pm 70^\circ$ outside layers. It is interesting to note that the $\pm 70^\circ$ layers show very few transverse cracks, as is evident in the figure. More detailed quantitative and qualitative description of the fatigue damage development will be the subject of a future paper.

Figure 8 Micrographs of damaged specimens tested at $R = 0.05$ and
(a) $p_{\max} = 55.2$ MPa, (b) $p_{\max} = 27.6$ MPa

FATIGUE LIFE

Figure 9 shows the test results in terms of operating pressure range Δp , versus the number of cycles to failure, N_f , for both R ratios. The figure also shows the corresponding least square regression lines (best fit). The damaging effect of high mean pressure (i.e. tests with $R = 0.3$)

is clearly evident from the figure. For the same Δp , the corresponding N_f is about four times smaller for $R = 0.3$ than for $R = 0.05$ tests.

Figure 9 Operating Pressure Range versus Number of Cycles to Failure

CONCLUSION

An experimental study has been conducted on the fatigue behaviour of multi-directional filament wound fibreglass/epoxy tubes. Commercially available tubes were tested at two pressure ratios, viz. $R = 0.05$ and 0.3 . From the recorded hysteresis loops, a progressive stiffness change is observed in both the transverse and axial directions. The ratcheting strain in the transverse direction is of the same magnitude for both R -ratios and four pressure ranges. For all tests, extensive delamination through the 0° layer and transverse cracking of $\pm 45^\circ$ layers are observed. The damaging effect of high mean pressure is clearly evident from the results.

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